

REHABILITATION OF PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES

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Annotation: Individuals with physical disabilities constitute a social group that is very diverse in terms of the type of body dysfunction, degree of impairment, time and causes of the emergence of disability, and the possibility of independent functioning in the local environment. Common features of physical disabilities include the threat of marginalization, poverty, and social exclusion, which are often based on stereotypes. Most individuals with physical disabilities require rehabilitation, and not only medical rehabilitation. Individuals with physical disabilities also need social rehabilitation which is important for quality of life. An effective rehabilitation process needs to be adapted to the individual capabilities and needs of the patient, ensuring respect for his/her subjectivity and dignity during the therapy process. The rehabilitation process will need to overcome psychological barriers that hinder the creation of positive motivation for perseverance and effort in striving for the fullest possible participation in community life – at local, family, and professional levels. Contemporary active social policy, as well as, scientific and technical progress, and widespread computerization of life in all areas means that people with physical disability have more opportunities for professional work and comprehensive personal development. These opportunities are particularly important for individuals within the so-called 'working age', and will provide richer involvement in the mainstream of social life.

Keywords: physical disability, social rehabilitation, disabled people.

Introduction

Since the first days of independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has paid great attention to solving the social problems of disabled people. Back in November 1991, the Law "On Social Protection of Disabled Persons" was adopted. Over the past 23

years of independence, many laws, regulations and state programs have been adopted aimed at ensuring social protection of disabled people. The Republic of Uzbekistan was one of the first, on February 27, 2009, to sign the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. The new version of the basic law enshrining the rights of disabled people in Uzbekistan, "On Social Protection of Disabled Persons", adopted on July 11, 2008, enshrines most of the provisions of the Convention [1]. A number of regulatory documents were adopted to implement the new legislation. Among the most significant are the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers "On measures to improve the management structure and organization of the medical and labor examination service", "On approval of the Regulation Senior Lecturer of the Department of Fundamentals of Building a Democratic Society in Uzbekistan.

Research Intern of the Department of Fundamentals of Building a Democratic Society in Uzbekistan. Social structure, social institutions and processes 159 on the individual rehabilitation program for disabled people”, “On approval of the Regulation on the procedure for reserving jobs for employment of persons in need of social protection”. In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has formed the main directions of social protection of disabled people, aimed at the maximum possible integration of disabled people into society, the creation of a system of rehabilitation of disabled people, and the formation of an accessible living environment.

One of the most effective methods of including people with disabilities in a full life is obtaining an education. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, education of people with disabilities is carried out in two directions: differentiated education in specialized educational institutions and inclusive education of people with disabilities in general educational institutions. There are 86 specialized schools and boarding schools, 23 sanatorium-type boarding schools, 122 special preschool institutions in the republic, where children with disabilities receive correctional assistance. Social rehabilitation activities include medical and restorative work, correctional education and upbringing, social and labor orientation due to the specifics of the disease. By the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 17, 2007 "On the activities of specialized professional colleges for people with disabilities" in the republic 4 colleges were created, in which over 1,500 students with limited physical

and intellectual abilities study. Graduates of special boarding schools for children with musculoskeletal disorders and general diseases are admitted to regular academic lyceums and professional colleges of the republic every year and study in the integrated education system. However, it must be recognized that the currently established system of integrated education is only available to people who do not have significant limitations in life activity [2]. An important task in the field of rehabilitation of disabled people is their employment. In accordance with the law "On social protection of disabled people", a minimum number of jobs are reserved in the institutions and organizations of the republic for the employment of disabled people in the amount of at least three percent of the number of employees. Based on this provision, since 2010, about 20,000 quota jobs for disabled people have been created annually in the republic.

The experience of rehabilitation of disabled people in Great Britain is noteworthy, where care for people with disabilities is provided by a large number of organizations, namely: private homeowners, the public sector and local authorities. In Great Britain, the main emphasis is on the ability of a disabled person to take care of himself independently, for this purpose, social centers help disabled people to acquire certain skills, for example, shopping in stores, cooking independently, the ability to independently manage money, visiting public places, developing fine motor skills, which is ensured in handicraft classes, physiotherapy, drawing, reading, etc. For people with severe disabilities, rehabilitation is carried out directly in the boarding schools and boarding houses themselves, as well as in clinics or outpatient clinics, in addition, there is a practice of placing a disabled person in a hospital for a certain period for the purpose of rest for his relatives. Another positive experience of Great Britain is the development and functioning of occupational therapy, where a specialist in this field provides multifaceted assistance to a disabled person, starting with a simple consultation and going on to changing the layout of the house. Each hospital has an occupational therapy department, where a social worker and an occupational therapist develop a joint program for each client. This program is agreed upon directly with the client and his family. In social services in Great Britain, there are special services for hiring disabled people for work. In Germany, there is a Social Security Code, where Chapter IX "Rehabilitation und Teilhabe behinderter Menschen" aims to encourage self-

determination and equal participation in society of disabled people and people at risk of disability, as well as to prevent or counteract deprivation. Rehabilitation of disabled people in Germany goes through several stages:

- 1) provision of medical services - preference is given to the outpatient method;
- 2) assistance in acquiring certain skills for subsequent employment.

The peculiarity of rehabilitation of disabled people in Germany is that the state and society do this at the earliest stages, even when the disease is detected, with subsequent reduction or complete elimination of the disease, which can lead to disability.

Foreign investment projects and public funds provide great assistance in the rehabilitation of disabled people. The joint project of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Population of the Republic of Uzbekistan and UNDP in Uzbekistan "ACCESS" helps to introduce elements of advanced foreign experience into the education system. Cooperation with such international organizations as UNESCO, UNICEF, the Asian Development Bank, the Fund for Support of Social Initiatives (FSSI) has a positive impact on the integration of children with special educational needs. Under the program of the pilot project of UNICEF and the Ministry of Public Education "Organization of support centers for inclusive-correlative education" in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Andijan, Namangan, Surkhandarya, Khorezm and Fergana regions, more than 6,000 disabled children were examined, of which about 600 were integrated into general education schools. The SISF project developed and is gradually implementing the Concept for the Development of Inclusive Education in Samarkand, Navoi, Termez. Starting from the 2010-2011 academic year, the SISF project continued the implementation of inclusive education in 12 academic lyceums and professional colleges in Angren, Jizzakh, Samarkand, Kokand, Karshi and Termez.

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